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Teachers' Classroom Management as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined teachers' classroom management as predictors of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study was 21,272 students in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 1,064 students (that is, 5% of students' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The instrument 'Teachers' Classroom Management Questionnaire (TCMQ)' was used for data collection while Students' Academic Performance Scores (SAPS) was used to measure students' academic performance for this study. The instrument (TCMQ) was subjected to content and construct validation. Content validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficient values of 0.83 for TCMQ was obtained and considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that classroom arrangement and social isolation positively and significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that applying good teachers' classroom management is essential for students' academic success in the classroom in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that teachers should be cautious while using social isolation in the classroom so that it does adversely affect students' academic performance in the school.

Keywords: Teachers' classroom management and students' academic performance

INTRODUCTION

Education is regarded as a powerful instrument of social change and national development. It is the process of imparting knowledge, skills, values, ethics, principles and rules with a view to improve the quality of life of an individual. Education is seen as the light that drives away darkness of ignorance and enables mankind to find its way through the tortures and labyrinth of development and civilization. This is so considering that education is one of the instruments for economic progress, social mobilization, political survival and effective technological development.(Soentan 2020,Osegbue et al 2018). Meaning that any nation which has a decline in the quality of education at any level will have a far reaching negative impact on the nation's moral, civic, cultural and economic sustainability. Though one of the major problem facing Nigerian education is low level of student's performance in both local and standardized examination.(Enwereji et al 2022)

For a nation to achieve the goals of her education, teachers as key implementers of any educational programme must be put into perspective in order to help improve academic performance of students which is the core objective.

Academic performance is a broad concept that refers to the level of achievement attained by students in their educational pursuits. It can be measured through various means such as grades, test scores, participation in extracurricular activities and attendance. Academic performance is an important aspect of education, as it serves as an indicator of the quality of education that students receive and their potential for success in their future careers. Onyejekwe et al (2025a) sees academic performance as a student's success in meeting academic expectations, such as getting good grades, participating in class and understand the material. It is a measure of student's ability to apply knowledge, engage with their studies and master subject matter.

All the learning actions among students towards obtaining scores from teacher-made test and examinations among others are known as students' academic performance. Academic performance is the measurement of students' success across various academic subjects. It is students' achievement and success in their educational pursuits such as overall GPA grade point average, standardized test scores, and educational aspirations and attainment. It can be the attainment or success of students in knowledge, skill and appreciations taught in schools. It can also be the percentage of marks obtained in their academic subjects at the test examinations. It represents achievement outcomes that indicate the extent to which a person has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional environments, specifically in school, college, and university. Nwike *et al.* (2024) opined that secondary school system mostly defined cognitive goals that either apply across multiple subject areas (example, critical thinking) or include the acquisition of knowledge and understanding in a specific intellectual domain (example, numeracy, literacy, science, history). Academic performance is generally used to determine how well an individual is able to assimilate, retain, recall and communicate his knowledge of what has been learnt. Okafor (2022) asserted that academic performance is the demonstrated achievement of learning as opposed to the potential for learning. In this study Academic performance refers to the ability of students to demonstrate knowledge and skills acquired through various learning processes, including formal education. It is a critical aspect of students' development and an essential factor in determining future success in higher education and career prospects. Academic performance is often measured using standardized assessments, course grades, and other metrics.

Academic performance is regarded as excellence in all academic disciplines, in class as well as in co-curricular activities. Asiegbu *et al.* (2022) submitted that academic performance is the knowledge gained after assessment has been done by a teacher to meet educational goals as enshrined in the curriculum for a fixed time period. Meanwhile, for these goals to be achieved, it requires continuous assessment or examination results. Academic performance of students is not only a guide to the efficacy of a specific school, but also a significant determinant of the future of young people in particular and the nation at large. Learner's outcomes have become a common subject of discussion in all fields of education because they are important for the future state of a particular nation and thus causing scholars to carryout numerous studies to unravel factors that militate against good academic performance.

If teachers are dissatisfied, frustrated, uninspired and unmotivated, the nation's educational system is doomed, because educational goals cannot be met without them. Ekechukwu and Ifeanyichukwu (2021) asserted that the willingness of teachers to cooperate, relate well and work effectively with their students is largely determined by their classroom management. Classroom management is one of the neglected areas in our secondary schools, despite the fact that the success or failure of any teaching and learning process depends on the way classroom are managed. Failure to effectively manage the classroom can have an overall negative influence on the entire school, especially in terms of sound academic performance of the school. When this happens other negative consequences follow such as the depletion of the student population of the school because parent/guardians prefer to enroll their children and ward in schools that are performing well academically.

Teachers' classroom management is a significant part of effective teaching and learning process. Due to an effective classroom management, students flourish in a positive class climate and a compassionate environment. From a students' perspective, effective classroom management provides them the opportunities to socialize themselves while learning. From teachers' perspective, effective classroom management involves precautionary discipline and fruitful teaching. Furthermore, classroom management is the process of organizing and conducting the business of the classroom, many perceive it as the preservation of order through teachers' control. Classroom management is much more than that; Nwankwoala (2022) submitted that classroom management involves the establishment and maintenance of the classroom environment so that educational goals can be accomplished.

Classroom management is a skill that can be acquired like any other profession. It is a skill that must be practiced to achieve proficiency. Classroom management thus requires specific skills such as planning organizing, as well as an aptitude for team work. It requires a great deal of commitment, initiatives, teachers' willingness to adjust, creative thinking and actions (Ekwelunde *et al.*, 2023). Teachers' classroom management plays an important role in the teaching and learning process. It is a veritable tool in the process of instructional delivery in the classroom. The success of any educational system is a function of the effectiveness of classroom management. Assimonye *et al.* (2023) averred that classroom management is the actions teachers take to create a supportive environment for the academic and social emotional learning of students. Classroom teachers are managers and so ought to be in control from the beginning of the lesson to the end so as to ensure that the students benefit from the interactive business that transpires in the classroom situation. Onyejekwe *et al.* (2025a) sees classroom management as the action that the teacher takes to create and maintain a learning environment that is conducive to successful instruction. This to a great extent would enhance smooth coordination and responses on the part of both the teacher and the learner.

Classroom management is a comprehensive term for a variety of teacher actions designed to improve learning. Classroom management usually refers to management of physical environment and instructional materials (Chinedu & Chinwendu, 2021). It also concerns with the organization of non-academic task such as checking of class attendance, record keeping of class progress, monitoring and regulating the activities and behaviour of students, maintaining order and disorder which are essential for teaching and learning. Similarly Ohamobi and Edor(2025) sees classroom management as planning arrangement and care of the classroom to ensure that it is convenient for teaching and learning. In contributing to effective classroom management by the teacher, Asiegbu *et al.* (2022) maintained that there should be necessary equipment to help the teachers manage the class with ease. A good classroom manager makes good instruction possible. Domike *et al.* (2019) stated that effective classroom management is a must in terms of teaching and learning to occur uneventfully along with positive outcomes. Classroom management plays a pivotal role in constructive interactions that support successful classroom environments for both teachers and students .The knowledge and experience students acquire in the classroom helps them to socialize with the people within and outside the school environment.(onyekazi *et al.*,2022)The majority of disciplinary problems in classes may be attributed to teachers' incompetence in classroom management

Contextually, the researchers defined teachers' classroom management as the exercise of managerial control over class activities, it has to do with supervising, controlling, co-coordinating, directing of students, classroom activities in order to achieve the set educational goals. Classroom management is one of the neglected areas in our public secondary schools, despite the fact that the success or failure of any teaching and learning process depends on the way classroom are managed. Failure to effectively manage the classroom can have an overall negative influence on the entire school, especially in terms of sound academic performance of the school. When this happens other negative consequences follow such as the depletion of the student population of the school because parents/guardians prefer to enroll their children and ward in schools that are performing well academically. In this study, teachers' classroom management was limited to teachers' classroom arrangement and teachers' use of social isolation.

Teachers' classroom arrangement is an important factor in the process of teaching and classroom management. Sergin and Eranil (2023) noted that a good classroom seating arrangement is the cheapest form of classroom management. It is discipline free. This implies that a poorly arranged class could be a potential source of discipline problems. Azubuike (2021) submitted that teachers' classroom arrangement is the order or way a teacher puts in place all that are placed under his care in the classroom. Also, the way the teacher arranges the classroom plays an important role in classroom management. The seating arrangement of the students must necessarily be such that facilitates not only the students' view of the chalkboard but also the interaction of the students with one another and with the teacher for academic purposes. This implies that the seating arrangement should facilitate the movement of the teacher within the classroom, so that he can have a feel of the students' activities while he is doing the teaching. This shows that the teacher should understand that the physical environment is the framework of learning that can contribute to either promoting or impeding learning. Adeyemo (2019) stated that classroom arrangement has to do with how a teacher puts in order all the physical objects that are found in his class. He asserted that classroom management comprises the sitting arrangements, chalkboard arrangement, placement of the maps and other teaching aids so as to allow easy movement of both the teacher and the students in order to avoid misbehaviour and promote quality teaching and learning. Thus, teachers' proper classroom arrangement promotes good use of social isolation in the classroom.

Teachers' use of social isolation of students as a means of punishment in schools is to modify their behaviours and bring out the best in them. Social isolation is a state of complete or near-complete lack of contact between an individual and society. It differs from loneliness, which reflects temporary and involuntary lack of contact with other humans in the world. Social isolation can be an issue for individuals of any age, though symptoms may differ by age group (Mohammed *et al.*, 2022). Social isolation has similar characteristics in both temporary instances and for those with a historical lifelong isolation cycle. Sergin and Eranil (2023) asserted that all types of social isolation can include staying alone in the house for long period of time, having no communication with family, acquaintances or friends, and/or willfully avoiding any contact with other humans when those opportunities do arise. Social isolation is often used to decrease undesirable behaviour. The teacher might decide to set the student aside for the meantime as a result of a particular misbehaviour. The teacher must be careful when using this method so that other negative behaviours are not strengthened. Thus, ineffective classroom management through teachers' use of social isolation might lead to poor teacher-student relationship in the classroom.

The ever-increasing fluctuations in academic performance of students in public secondary schools are a serious concern and unpalatable signal to the development of the economy. This continues to militate against the objectives of education to provide students with basic knowledge in various concepts and principles through efficient selection of content and sequencing. These laudable objectives are not being achieved as the performance of students in English Language and Mathematics has been fluctuating consistently. The fluctuating rate of academic performance of students in English Language and Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State is becoming more worrisome than envisaged. The abysmal academic performance of students in West African Examinations Council (WAEC), and the National Examinations Council (NECO) is alarming that one begins to wonder if teachers possess the quality and apply proper teacher-student classroom engagement strategies in managing students in school. Evidence from the report of WAEC chief examiner's report (2023) showed that students' academic performance in English Language and Mathematics in WAEC reduced by 8 per cent between 2021 and 2023 while students' academic performance in English Language and Mathematics in NECO was reduced by 12 per cent between 2021 and 2023. This however necessitated the researchers to carry out an analytic examination of teachers' classroom management as predictor of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine teachers' classroom management as a predictor of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the predicative value of teachers' use of classroom arrangement on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. find out the predicative value of teachers' use of social isolation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predicative value of teachers' use of classroom arrangement on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predicative value of teachers' use of social isolation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Teachers' use of classroom arrangement does not significantly predict students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Teachers' use of social isolation does not significantly predict students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODS

The study examined teachers' classroom management as predictors of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study was 21,272 students in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 1,064 students (that is, 5% of students' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The instrument 'Teachers' Classroom Management Questionnaire (TCMQ)' was used for data collection while Students' Academic Performance Scores (SAPS) was used to measure students' academic performance for this study. The instrument (TCMQ) was subjected to content and construct validation. Content validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach Alpha technique and the average coefficient values of 0.83 for TCMQ was obtained and considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Out of 1,064 copies of the instrument administered, 825(78%) of the instrument were correctly completed and returned. Simple regression analysis was used for the study.

RESULTS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: *What is the predicative value of classroom arrangement on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis on the predicative value of classroom arrangement on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	23.942	5.151	
Classroom Arrangement	0.477	0.365	0.452
R	0.452		
R ²	0.417		
Adj. R ²	0.396		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that classroom arrangement positively predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.452$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.417 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 42% of the variations in students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in classroom arrangement. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.396 indicating that 40% of the total variation in the dependent variable (students' academic performance) was explained by the independent variable (classroom arrangement). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of classroom arrangement is moderately strong in determining the students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Again, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.452$) showed that classroom arrangement is a positive predictor of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in classroom arrangement led to 0.452(45%) increase in students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of classroom arrangement on students' academic performance means that students' academic performance moderately depends on classroom arrangement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Two: *What is the predicative value of social isolation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis on the predicative value of social isolation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	17.884	6.239	
Social Isolation	0.413	0.458	0.395
R	0.395		
R ²	0.346		
Adj. R ²	0.311		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that social isolation positively predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.395$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.346 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 35% of the variations in students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in social isolation. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a

value of 0.311 indicating that 31% of the total variation in the dependent variable (students' academic performance) was explained by the independent variable (social isolation). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of social isolation is moderately strong in determining the students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Additionally, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.395$) showed that social isolation is a positive predictor of students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit increase in social isolation led to 0.395(40%) increase in students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of social isolation on students' academic performance means that students' academic performance moderately depends on social isolation in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Classroom arrangement does not significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of significance on the simple regression analysis on significant predication of classroom arrangement on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized <i>B</i>	Std. Dev. <i>B</i>	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	23.942	5.151		23.208	0.000
Classroom Arrangement	0.477	0.365	0.452	21.435	0.000
R	0.452				
R ²	0.417				
Adj. R ²	0.396				
F	30.225				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.452 while the R^2 is 0.417 and Adjust R^2 is 0.396. The F-ratio associated with regression is 30.225, the t-test is 21.435 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that classroom arrangement does not significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that classroom arrangement significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Social isolation does not significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance on the simple regression analysis on significant predication of social isolation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized <i>B</i>	Std. Dev. <i>B</i>	Standardized <i>B</i>	t- value	p- value
Constant	17.884	6.239		19.736	0.000
Social Isolation	0.413	0.458	0.395	15.264	0.000
R	0.395				
R ²	0.346				
Adj. R ²	0.311				
F	24.512				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.395 while the R^2 is 0.346 and Adjust R^2 is 0.311. The F-ratio associated with regression is 24.512, the t-test is 15.264 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that classroom arrangement does not significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that classroom arrangement significantly predict students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Findings on the predictive value of teachers' classroom arrangement on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that teachers' classroom arrangement has a positive predictive value of 0.451(45%) on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that improvement in teachers' classroom arrangement would bring about 45% improvements in students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The study also showed that teachers' classroom arrangement significantly predicts students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings are in consonance with the findings of Ekwelunde *et al.* (2023) that teachers arrange their classrooms to enhance teaching and learning in the classroom which can come through arranging students to facilitate task behaviour, removing distracting materials, organizing audio-visual aids, strategically placing students with special needs, keeping neat and tidy classroom. This implies that effective classroom arrangement by teachers enhance classroom management for teaching and learning. This means that teachers' classroom arrangement is an important factor in the process of teachers' classroom management and control. This agrees with Okafor and Enemuo (2024) findings that teachers should possess the necessary skill in class arrangement for efficient teaching and learning. The seats, desks should be well arranged in rows. The result of this study is also in agreement with Akuezulo and Egenti (2024) findings that classroom arrangement is better practiced in private secondary school than in public secondary. Furthermore, the physical arrangement of the classroom is one of the basic classroom principles every teacher must possess to enhance quality teaching and learning for improved students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Findings on the predictive value of social isolation on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that social isolation has a positive predictive value of 0.395(40%) on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This means that a change in social isolation would bring about 40% changes in students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study also showed that social isolation significantly predicts students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings are in agreement with the findings of Mohammed *et al.* (2022) that teachers use to separate erring student(s) in order to get them to concentrate in the classroom activities. The findings of Sevgin and Ernil (2023) also agreed with the findings of the study that teachers' relations with students are crucial for their academic performance when engage students with concentrating classroom activities like separating disturbing students to focus without distractions from their peers. Assimonye *et al.* (2023) findings are in line with the findings of the study that healthy connection between students and teachers must permit full engagement in school issues as this will allow students to express their thoughts and have their beliefs weighed and corrected if they are incorrect. Okafor and Enemuo (2024) averred that the interaction between students and teachers should be warm and cordial for smooth information transfer and effective students' academic performance in schools.

CONCLUSION

From the results of this study, teacher-student relationship and teachers' classroom management positively and significantly predicted students' academic performance in public secondary schools in

Anambra State. In conclusion, building and maintaining positive teacher-student relationships and applying good teachers' classroom management is essential for students' academic success in the classroom in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Therefore students' classroom behaviour can be improved through an enhancement in the relationships between teachers and students and good teachers' classroom management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should practice classroom arrangement in assigning responsibilities to students to make them have full participation in the learning process. This will help students to develop and have stronger social skills.
2. Teachers should be cautious while using social isolation in the classroom so that it does adversely affect students' academic performance in the school.

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